

**CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
BAYERO UNIVERSITY KANO**

In Partnership with

**Institut National De La Recherche Agronomique
Du Niger, Maradi, Niger Republic**

Organizes a
**5-DAY
TRAINING
WORKSHOP**

On

**FISH HATCHING,
CULTURE &
MANAGEMENT**

Held @

INRAN – CERRA, MARADI

13 – 17 MARCH, 2023

LESSON ONE (1)

INTRODUCTION

Fish culture (Aquaculture) which refers to the rearing and/or production of fish is a very important business enterprise that connects food production, income generation, and job creation. It can be done in earthen/concrete ponds, plastic tanks, wooden vats, other convenient water-holding containers, etc.

REASONS FOR FISH FARMING

- Income/wealth and job creation
- Fish is an essential source of food
- Easily adaptable to our environments
- It is easy to culture

IMPORTANCE OF FISH FARMING

- It provides employment
- It is a source of income
- It is a source of Omega-3 fatty acids

THE AIMS OF THIS WORKSHOP

- To provide employment opportunities
- To enhance wealth creation, food security, and the rural economy
- Awareness creation about different value chains in fish production
- Training of youth particularly women for self-employment

PROBLEMS FACING AQUACULTURE

- Lack of capital
- Lack of technical know-how
- Lack of business plan
- Lack of good water source
- Lack of space
- Improper location of farm

Categories of Fish Production

- Fingerlings production

Stages of Development of African Catfish from Egg

Catfish Egg

Catfish hatched larvae with yolk sac

Catfish fry after losing yolk sac

Catfish fingerling in development

- Table size fish production

- **Brood stock production**

- **Fish feed production**

Funsab En... · In stock
Vital Feed - Funsab Ent...

HTS Farms · In stock
Aqualis Extruded Fish ...

Afrimash.com
Vital Fish Feed Pellets for Catfish ...

Funsab En... · In stock
Topfeed - Funsab Enter...

Bags of commercial Fish Feeds

- **Fish pond construction**

- **Artificial spawning (induced Ovulation & fertilization)**

LESSON TWO

ARTIFICIAL SPAWNING OF CATFISH

INTRODUCTION

- Step by step procedures on spawning process of catfish

SOME ARTIFICIAL SPAWNING MATERIALS

1. Brood stock (parent stock)
2. Hormone
3. Hatching tray
4. Water Quality kit
5. Nursery pond
6. Aerator
7. Razor
8. Syringe
9. Knife
10. Hand glove
11. Normal saline
12. Small bowl
13. Table
14. Syphoning tube
15. Hand towel
16. Tissue paper

SELECTION OF BROODSTOCK

- 300 – 800 g of at least 8-month-old
- Sex identification:
 - ❖ Females are big in size
 - ❖ Females have a fat body
 - ❖ The male head is bigger
 - ❖ The dorsal fin of male fish is longer and brighter
 - ❖ They all have reproductive organs, but the male organ (genital papilla) is a bit pointed & elongated

MATURITY AND OVULATION OF FISH EGGS

The steps are as follows:

- Injecting the female with a hormone or pituitary gland
- It is normally done at night, after separating the intended one in a small container.
- The quantity of hormone (ml) depends on the weight of the female fish

STRIPPING THE EGGS FROM THE FEMALE FISH

- Ovulation takes place early during hot weather
- Two people are required for egg stripping
- The stripping of eggs is done gently into a clean dry container

MILT EXTRACTION

- Sacrifice the male
- Dissect the male and bring out the milt sack, clean the blood with wool or tissue paper

STEP ONE

- Apply the milt on the eggs
- Apply normal saline solution to the milt
- Pour the milt onto the eggs for fertilization
- Stir the mixture for about 1 – 3 mins

STEP TWO

- Oxygenated water with a temperature range of 28 to 32 °C is required
- The hatching pond/tank should be filled with clean water
- Spread the fertilized eggs on the hatching tray
- After 24 – 48 hrs. the fries will be visible in the water

STEP THREE

- Remove the hatching tray after hatching to prevent contamination
- The hatchlings will not be fed for three (3) days
- From day 3 the fries will be fed with Artemia for 2 weeks
- The water will be siphoned daily
- After artemia, the fries will be fed with 0.3-0.5mm feed for 4 – 6 weeks

STEP FOUR

- Fries are fed after every 2 hours
- The size of the fish determines its feed size from 0.3 – 12mm
- Sorting is done to prevent cannibalism
- Frequent water change is necessary
- Do not stress the fries
- Frequent siphoning is highly required

SUMMARY

- The above steps should be followed to achieve a good result
- Proper maintenance and supervision are necessary
- Clean water is compulsory in artificial spawning

LESSON THREE

INTRODUCTION TO FISH DISEASES AND MEDICATION

PREVENTION

- Curing fish disease is costly & time-consuming
- Prevention is better than cure

DISEASE SYMPTOMS IN FISH

1. Standstill in an upright position
2. Congestion at the water inlet
3. Inability to feed
4. Seclusion from the group
5. White lesion/decoloration on the skin
6. Swollen skin, etc.
7. Rottenness on fins, barbels & other body parts
8. Sore on the body of fish

PREVENTIVE MEASURES

- Allow the pond to dry properly before restocking
- Apply ash/lime to earthen ponds before restocking
- Weeding of the pond area is essential
- Preventive measures should be against reptiles and predators
- Stock your fish from a good source
- Avoid overstocking pond
- Observe regular feeding time
- Observe proper hygiene
- Avoid contaminated feeds
- Remove dead fish immediately to avoid contamination

SUMMARY

If symptoms persist, consult a veterinary (fish) doctor

FEEDING TECHNIQUES

INTRODUCTION

- A well-fed fish grows optimally and yield high profit in short time
- A malnourished fish will be stunted and become vulnerable to diseases leading loss of investment

REASONS FOR FEEDING

- To provide complete nutrients required
- Rapid growth
- Good profit margin

METHODS OF FEEDING

- Hand (broadcasting) method

- Mechanized (automated) feeding

FEEDING RULES

- Regular feeding on a spot
- Avoid over feeding
- Do not feed during harvest
- Avoid early feeding during cold weather

FEEDING TIMES IN A DAY

- 2 – 3 feeding times for adult
- 1kg and above can be fed once daily
- Feeds should be consumed within 15 mins of administering
- Weather condition determines feeding

TYPES OF FISH FOOD/FEED

- Natural
- Supplement
- Complete

Complete is expensive but has the following advantages:

- 1- It provides room for large scale production
- 2- Fast growth rate
- 3- It is profitable

SUMMARY

- Features of complete feed:
 - ❖ It comprises all the required nutrients
 - ❖ Palatability
 - ❖ Floating capacity
 - ❖ Standard in size (from 0.30mm – 12mm).
 - ❖ A well-fed fish is a healthy fish

FISH FARM SITING AND POND CONSTRUCTION

INTRODUCTION

- Fish farm siting and pond construction
 - ❖ A fish pond is an excavated ditch (earthen or concrete) that has water retention capacity for fish farming
 - ❖ It can be small or big depending on the intent of the farmer
 - ❖ It can be for subsistent/commercial

Other facilities include:

- 1- Robber tank
- 2- Cage
- 3- Tarpaulin
- 4- Wooden vat/trough
- 5- Jerry can

THINGS TO CONSIDER BEFORE SITING A FISH FARM

- Availability & accessibility of water
- soil with water holding capacity for earthen pond
- Not a rocky area
- Not a bushy area
- Secured place
- Proximity to market (for input/output)
- Size of pond and its depth
- It should not exceed 1-2 meters in depth
- It should have inlet & outlet

IMPORTANT POINTS

- The pond environment should always be clean and tidy
- Avoid leakages in ponds and tanks
- Avoid grazing in pond area
- After 12 – 18 months, pond water should be drained and sun dried

SUMMARY

- well-constructed pond last longer and save maintenance cost

WATER QUALITY AND ITS MAINTENANCE

Introduction

- Clean water is always needed in fish farming
- Clean water enhances the following:
 - Fast growth
 - Healthy fish with good immunity

FACTORS ENHANCING CLEANLINESS OF WATER

- Its source
- Nature of the pond
- Feeding and medication
- Concentration of dissolved oxygen increases with solar radiation

REQUIRED FISH TEMPERATURE

- 28 – 32⁰C
- Below 28⁰C, eating and growth will be slow.

SUMMARY

Important points to note:

- Fish wellbeing
- Regular feeding at required rate
- Change of water when due
- Polluted water should be changed
- If there is algal bloom in the water, it should be changed partially

LESSON FOUR

INTRODUCTION

- Harvesting is a significant stage in fish farming because it is the stage one realizes profit or otherwise

HARVESTING

- It is preferably done early in the morning
- Fish should be kept in a clean water after harvest
- Do not feed fish 24 hours before harvest

METHODS OF FISH HARVEST

The size of pond determines the method to be use

- Draining of pond water

- Use of hook and line
- Use of Cast net
- Use of Seine Net
- Clamp Net
- Drag Net
- Scoop Net
- Malian Trap

Hook and line

Seine net

SCOOP NET

It is use during sampling, sorting and partial harvest from a shallow pond, tank, etc.

CLAP NET

DRAG NET

OTHER FISHING GEARS THAT ARE USED FOR CATCHING FISH

CONTAINERS USED FOR TRANSPORTING FISH

ENCLOSED TANK

It is used for transporting live fish to a far place after harvest.

POST HARVEST & PRESERVATION METHODS

Fish can be preserved after harvesting in different ways, such as:

NOTE:

- Cool environment is required
- Reduction of moisture content of the fish
- Clean & tidy container is required

FISH ICING

FISH SALTING

FISH DRYING

FISH SMOKING

CANNING

FISH MARKETING

FISH MARKETING

Marketing depends on:

- Market proximity
- Marketing segmentation
- Market demand
- Precautionary measures during harvest

